

SPECIAL ASPECTS OF THE TRANSLATION OF COLLOCATIONS

Kaxarova Madina Baxodirovna

English teacher at the Interfaculty foreign languages department
of Bukhara State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10142783>

Abstract. This article discusses detailed study of some issues related to the characteristics of English collocations, phrases, phraseological units and the problems of translating them into Uzbek and Russian. The interest in translating collocations comes from their great importance in language. Translators and students face problems and difficulties in translating collocations

Keywords: Collocations, Translating Collocations, language, method, phrase.

INTRODUCTION

Learning English is widespread in our country. Good knowledge of the language, including English, is impossible without knowledge of its phraseology. Knowledge of phraseology makes it extremely easy to read both non-fiction literature and fiction literature. It is very important to teach students the ability to understand and correctly translate the phraseological units of the studied language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

As you know, the structure of the English language differs from the structure of the Uzbek language, and from a genetic point of view, they belong to different language families. Consequently, the grammatical structure of these languages also differs from each other. For example, in the Uzbek language there are many affixes, a sentence begins with a noun and ends with a verb, there are no prepositions, articles, gender categories and in English, on the contrary, there are articles, prepositions, and affixes are not developed. Therefore, when studying and translating words, phrases, sentences, and especially phraseological units, certain difficulties arise. In addition, the mutual difference in the form and meaning of English, Uzbek and Russian phraseological units creates difficulties in their translation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Collocations are an important part in language and their translation seems to be more important especially if they are unfamiliar to students and belong to another culture and language.

The phrase, which ranks fourth after the word, has its own characteristics. When learning a foreign language, when translating from a foreign language into Uzbek (that is, our native language), this linguistic unit creates a certain complexity. Typical word combinations that regularly occur in English speech and writing are called collocations. In other words, collocations are those word combinations and short phrases which your English teacher asked you to memorize as examples of use when you studied new words. The verb "to collocate" has the following meanings: to place together, to arrange in proper order.

Usually, the translation of an unfamiliar phrase is based on the criteria given in the dictionary:

1. It contains the original and expressed concept of the word;
2. The relevance of the word to the subject under study;
3. Value of information;
4. Richness of lexical-syntactic combination;
5. Educational-methodical expediency¹.

¹ Khidekl S.S., Kaul M.R., Ginzburg E.L. Educational English-Russian dictionary of compatibility and difficulties of word use. - M.: Astrel. AST, 2002.

Unfortunately, monolingual and bilingual dictionaries of phrases based on English and Uzbek materials have not been created yet. This is the task of lexicographers.

A bilingual dictionary of phrases is a special dictionary and differs from other bilingual (translation) dictionaries in the following ways:

- the special meanings of the words are explained and the translation variant used in the situation is emphasized;
- the possibility of forming a compound in the separate meanings of words is revealed, the lexical-grammatical rules of their use in speech are offered.

In order to confirm the above points and to reveal the features of the translation of phrases, we will focus on the translation of some phrases mentioned in the dictionary. It can be said before that phrases, like words, in translation also imply the idea of an alternative in three different forms. In the literature on translation theory, it is argued that word and phraseological conformities look like words². They are:

1. Complete conformities.
2. Partial conformities.
3. Absence of conformities.

Now let's take a practical look at what the three types of conformities look like when translating English phrases into Uzbek.

U. Khoshimov and I.Yokubov³ in the book "Methods of teaching the English language" emphasized that the difficulties encountered in mastering words arise, first of all, in each word, based on its form, classified the difficulties arising in the study of phraseological units of the English language into 4 groups:

1) The first group includes international combinations that do not cause difficulties in their study. They are familiar to the students or meet in their native language. **For example: Achilles' heel** - a person is weak or vulnerable point; **flat broke** means not having any money at all; **right now** - this exact moment; **as for me house** — wife.

2) A characteristic feature of the second group is their belonging in their form and semantics only to one or another language. **For example: to leave school** (дословно: оставить школу) — *maktabni bitirmoq* (окончить школу); **beat the band** (дословно: побейте полосу) — *jon-jahdi bilan ishga kirishmoq* (энергично браться за работу). If we proceed from the form of turns, then it must be said that phraseological units in English begin with a verb, and in Uzbek, they begin with a noun and end with a verb. **Big fish** (дословно verbatim: большая рыба) — *obr'uli, katta lavozimdagi shaxs* (авторитетный, лицо большого чина). From a semantic point of view, this combination is found only in English (compare with colloquial Russian: **big shot**). Combination "Big fish" does not occur in the Uzbek language. It is applied in English to high officials.

CONCLUSION

These phraseological units cannot be defined by any one exact combination; therefore, they give rise to difficulties in assimilation. So that students do not make mistakes in the assimilation and translation of phraseological units of the English language, it is necessary to explain to them their meaning and cases of application, to explain that the difference in form and meaning is the

² Gafurov I., Muminov O.M., Qambarov N.M. Theory of translation. - Tashkent, 2012.

³ U. Khoshimov I., Yokubov I. Methods of teaching English. - Tashkent, 2013. 117p.

influence of the fact that these languages belong to different language families and, under the influence of this main factor, their phraseological layers in different situations and contexts can express different concepts and images. In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the translation of phraseological units from English into others presents significant difficulties.

References:

1. Gafurov I., Muminov O.M., Qambarov N.M. Theory of translation. - Tashkent, 2012.
2. Khidekl S.S., Kaul M.R., Ginzburg E.L. Educational English-Russian dictionary of compatibility and difficulties of word use. - M.: Astrel. AST, 2002.
3. U. Khoshimov I., Yokubov I. Methods of teaching English. - Tashkent, 2013. 117p.
4. Conceptual problems of world literature and linguistics in the sociocultural space of the XXI century: theory, methodology, practice. - T., 2009. C.314–315.
5. Jaroid Yu., Rud N. Osobennosti perevoda frazeologicheskix edinits. URL http://www.rusnauka.com/8_NND_201_0
6. Najmiddinovich, R. D. (2023). Increase jobs for transport companies in Uzbekistan by increasing the purchase of products manufactured by people with disabilities. American Journal of Business Management, Economics and Banking, 12, 128-130.
7. Bakirova H.B. Formation of lexical skills in learning foreign language terminology in a non-language university/ Emergent: journal of educational discoveries and lifelong learning (EJEDL) ISSN 2776- 0995 Vol. 2, Issue 5, 2021, Indonesia.
8. Кахарова М. Б. Boosting education quality is not myth anymore (from personal experience) // Молодой ученый. – 2016. – №. 14. – С. 544-546
9. Kaharova Madina Bakhodirovna. Perceptions of stress and the ways in which graduate students dealt with stress in the USA and Uzbekistan institutes // Проблемы педагогики. 2017. №5 (28).
10. Kaharova Madina Bakhodirovna. Group dynamics and the role play activities to raise awareness on social issues in the ESL classes // Проблемы педагогики. 2017. №5 (28).
11. Kaharova Madina Bakhodirovna. TESOL AND TETE INTERNATIONAL PROGRAMS RECOMMENDATIONS FOR TRAINING AND ORGANIZING SUCCESSFUL LESSONS. Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research. pp. 387-391. SSN: 2278-4853 Vol 10, Issue 10, October, 2021.
12. Kakharova Madina Bahodirovna, "INTERNATIONALIZING UNIVERSITIES AND STUDIES", IEJRD - International Multidisciplinary Journal, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 7, Jan. 2022.
13. Bakhodirovich, A. B. (2022). "Alchemist" Paolo Coelho. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 2(4), 105–108. Retrieved from <http://openaccessjournals.eu/index.php/ijdpp/article/view/1236>
14. Ahrorov Botir Bakhodirovich. (2022). Humanitarian values and social justice in Agatha Christie's "Ten little niggers" mystery novel. Eurasian Scientific Herald, 5, 96–99. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/esh/article/view/615>
15. Ahrorov Botir Baxodirovich. Some teaching techniques recommended by TESOL organization trainers and community to facilitate and conduct EFL lessons. "IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF PRIMARY EDUCATION: STRATEGY, INNOVATION AND BEST PRACTICES" INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE. Bukhara State University, Uzbekistan. p. 462. 20th Sep., 2021. In cooperation with Higher Education Ministry and Innovation Ministry.